

SURFACE CHARACTERIZATION OF COMPOSITES USED IN THE AIRCRAFT INDUSTRY BY AFM

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SUMMARY

Atomic Force Microscopy (AFM) has been used for the characterization of composite materials used in the aircraft industry. Force-distance curves have been obtained and adhesion forces have been compared with energy fracture toughness (G_{IC}) and XPS measurements. The correlation between AFM and G_{IC} shows the potential applicability of AFM for advanced characterization of composites.

Keywords: AFM composite surface force adhesion

INTRODUCTION

The Atomic Force Microscopy (AFM) technique has evolved into a useful and powerful tool for the advanced characterization of materials, gaining a place in many research and development laboratories of different industrial areas [1,2]. AFM is being applied to study phenomena such as abrasion, adhesion, cleaning, corrosion, etching, friction, lubrication and polishing, which could be used to solve processing and materials problems in a wide range of technologies affecting aerospace industry.

Advanced composite materials have been developed since 1960 in aerospace industry, taking advantage of their high performance, high specific stiffness and strength. The join of a composite is a critical process for the aircraft structures manufacturing and assembling. Adhesive bonding has reached great significance for structural joining technology, in detriment of over other joining methods such as mechanical fastening because it provides a homogenous stress distribution, low weight, high corrosion resistance, improved fatigue resistance and reduction in life-cycle maintenance costs [3,4]. No matter this, composite bonded joining performance is limited by the adhesive characteristics of the composite laminate surface, resulting sometimes in poor structural reliability.

The most commonly used manufacturing process for composites implies the curing of prepregged (prepreg) materials in autoclave. For this process, several prepreg plies (fibre wetted with resin) are placed on the tool and a vacuum bag is laid on this structure. Then, this assembly is positioned inside an autoclave, where the curing process takes place in the desired conditions of temperature and pressure. The vacuum bag is usually made of different ancillary materials (release agents, release films, peel-ply) in order to assure an appropriate compaction of the plies. During the contact

between the ancillary material and the prepreg, potential material transfer phenomena may have an impact on the adhesion behaviour of the composite surface, reducing the performance of the bonding.

In this work, AFM has been used for the advanced characterization of composite materials in order to characterize the adhesion behaviour of composite surfaces in contact with several release agents and release films during the curing process. Additional experiments for the characterization of composite material surfaces such as mechanical tests (interlaminar fracture toughness, G_{IC}) and elementary chemical composition determination of the surface (XPS) in order to correlate the AFM results have been also carried out.

EXPERIMENTATION

Materials

The composite material used in this study consists of a 180°C cure epoxy matrix reinforced with standard modulus carbon fibres. The material has been supplied as prepreg unidirectional tape.

For the interlaminar fracture toughness tests, a 180°C cure epoxy adhesive, supplied as a film with a carrier, has been used.

The different types of ancillary materials used to determine their influence on the resulting composite surface after curing are shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Ancillary materials used in this study.

Name	Supplied form	Chemical Characteristics
Release Agent (A1)	Liquid	Silicone
Release Agent (A2)	Liquid	Silicone
Release Film (F1)	Film	Fluorinated-ethylene-propylene (FEP)
Release Film (F2)	Film	Fluorinated-ethylene-propylene (FEP)

Sample preparation

Laminates for AFM and XPS, were manufactured from carbon/epoxy preimpregnated unidirectional tapes. They were made by laying up 8 plies using a vacuum bag, with different types of ancillary materials (F1, F2, A1 and A2) in contact with the composite surface during curing in autoclave at 180 °C and at suitable pressure for 120 minutes.

The test panels used for the interlaminar fracture toughness tests consisted of two laminates (previously cleaned with methyl-ethyl-ketone, MEK) bonded with an adhesive layer cured in autoclave. A thin film of PTFE was placed at the edge of the panels between the two laminates to act as a starting crack in the bonding line (figure 1). It should be mentioned that specific surface preparation procedures mandatory prior bonding for aircraft applications, were not applied to the laminates before bonding, in

order to be able to identify the behaviour of any potential transfer phenomenon and correlate the mechanical test results with the AFM and XPS results.

Figure 1. Scheme of the specimens used for the interlaminar fracture toughness tests.

Equipments

Atomic force microscope

The adhesion force has been measured by Atomic Force Microscopy (AFM) with a scanning probe microscope (Nanoscope IIIa, Multimode™ Digital Instrument) operating in force mode. There are different AFM working modes that depend on the contact between the sample and the tip: continuous contact (contact mode, force curve and lateral force), intermittent contact (tapping mode and phase contrast mode) and noncontact modes (attractive force mode, magnetic force microscopy, electric force microscopy, Kelvin probe, etc.).

For this study, contact mode and force curves have been used. In AFM contact mode, (also known as repulsive mode), the tip is in close contact with the sample while it is scanning the sample surface and the force between the tip and the sample is kept constant by moving up and down the samples. This movement is controlled by a piezoelectric mechanism and the deflection of the cantilever is measured by an optical device. The movement of the samples is directly related with the topography of the samples and, therefore, the contact mode provides an accurate quantitative analysis of surface micro-roughness of technological surfaces with the only limitation of the tip radius [1,5].

The force curve measurements describe the cantilever deflection as a function of the piezoelectric scanner travel. An example of force-distance curves obtained for the composite material in contact with ancillary materials A1 and F1 is shown in figure 2. As the tip gets closer to the sample surface it is lightly attracted by it (negative force)

but immediately it gets into contact with the sample surface and a positive force is observed. The penetration of the tip into the samples was made with 5 nN load and penetrations of about 100 nm were obtained for the different materials. The slopes in this part of the curve were equal for all materials because the elastic properties of sample and cantilever were similar. After indentation, the tip is retracted but it does not follow the same indentation curve because there is an adhesion force between tip and sample. When this force was equaled the tip released from the sample, and this force can be determined. In figure 2 it can be observed that the adhesion force of the composite samples manufactured in contact with release film F1 is smaller than the adhesion force measured on the samples manufactured in contact with release agent A1[5].

Figure 2. Force versus distance plot.

A silicon nitride tip (model MLCT-AUNM with an elastic constant of 0.05 N/m) has been used to carry out the force curves. For each sample, 200 adhesion measurements were obtained. Before every force curve test, the sample surface was scanned in contact mode with the AFM in order to measure the micro-roughness.

Measurements of local adhesive forces between a silicon nitride tip (Si_3N_4) and composite surfaces were performed at ambient conditions in air (25 °C and 40 % humidity). All different composite surfaces were tested with the same tip in order to ensure that the curvature tip radius and the cantilever spring constant did not change. Also, several experiments have been performed with other tips to confirm the same tendency. All experiments have been done with a threshold force of 5 nN to avoid permanent deformation on the composite surface.

Mechanical Tests

To determine the adhesive fracture toughness of the specimen, the critical applied mode I strain energy release rate for crack propagation (G_{IC}) was determined using a double cantilever beam (DCB) specimen as shown in Figure 1. Specimens were tested in INSTRON 4468 universal machine at room temperature and in “as received” conditions (RT/AR).

X-ray Photoelectron Spectroscopy

Photoelectron spectra (XPS) were obtained with a VG Escalab 200R spectrometer equipped with a hemispherical electron analyser (pass energy of 50 eV) and a MgK α ($h\nu = 1254.6$ eV, 1 eV = 1.6302×10^{-19} J) X-ray source, powered at 120 W. The kinetic energies of photoelectrons were measured using a hemispherical electron analyser working in the constant pass energy mode. The background pressure in the analysis chamber was kept below 2×10^{-8} mbar during data acquisition. The XPS data signals were taken in increments of 0.1 eV with dwell times of 50 ms. Binding energies were calibrated relative to the C 1s peak at 284.9 eV. High resolution spectra envelopes were obtained by curve fitting synthetic peak components using the software “*XPS peak*”. The raw data were used with no preliminary smoothing. Symmetric Gaussian-Lorentzian product functions were used to approximate the line shapes of the fitting components. Atomic ratios were computed from experimental intensity ratios and normalized by atomic sensitivity factors [6].

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The adhesion forces and micro-roughness measured by AFM for the composite samples manufactured using release agents and release films in contact with the composite surface during curing, are shown in Table 2. As it can be observed in Table 2, the pull-off force values obtained for the composite samples in contact with release agents (A1 and A2) during curing, are 60% higher than the pull-off forces obtained for the composite in contact with the release film samples (F1 and F2), suggesting that different adhesive mechanisms may be taking place in the surface of the samples

Adhesion forces measured by AFM have been found to be highly scattered as shown in table 2. As the AFM contact takes place in the nanometre range, any topographical defect in this scale, may modify the contact between the sample and the tip and therefore, the adhesion force are expected to be affected by the surface micro-roughness.

G_{IC} values and failure modes obtained for the specimens in contact with release agent (A1 and A2) and release films (F1 and F2) during curing are also shown in Table 2. As it can be observed, the best performance was obtained for the composite surfaces which were in direct contact with the release agents. On the other hand, the surfaces that were in contact with the release films showed a poor mechanical behaviour, especially in the case of using the release film F1.

Failure modes are also showed in table 2. The cohesive failure mode observed for A1 and A2 indicates good adhesion behaviour between the composite surface and the adhesive. However, adhesive failure mode found for F1 and F2 panels (adhesive failure) indicates a weak adhesion between the composite surface and the adhesive. Examples of G_{IC} specimens after testing are shown in Figure 3.

G_{IC} results and pull-off forces can be compared, so a higher adhesion force is related to higher fracture toughness energy. On the other hand, when the pull-off is smaller, fracture toughness energy is also smaller. There are differences in the values measured by AFM and by interlaminar fracture tests; this is due to type of tests. In the AFM it is

always tested the surface of the composite and there was no adhesive in the tip. This technique can provide adhesive forces from the surface but cannot determine if there would be a change in the bonded failure mode. Therefore, the quantitative correlation between AFM tests and interlaminar fracture ones could be only carried out if the failure mode is adhesive. No matter this, the AFM technique allows to classify the adhesive capability of a surface.

Table 2. Summary of AFM and mechanical test results

Ancillary Material	AFM				Mechanical tests		
	F _{adhesion}		Micro-roughness		G _{IC} (RT/AR)		
	Mean (nN)	St dev (σ)	Mean (nm)	St dev (σ)	Mean (J/m ²)	St dev (σ)	Failure mode
Release Agent (A1)	11	3	47	14	1348	6	Cohesive
Release Agent (A2)	12	3	36	10	1447	10	Cohesive
Release Film (F1)	8	1	8	3	54	13	Adhesive
Release Film (F2)	7	1	14	1	307	36	Adhesive

a) A1 specimen (cohesive failure)

b) F1 specimen (adhesive failure)

Figure 3. Examples of G_{IC} specimens after testing.

XPS results are shown in Table 3. For the composite surfaces cured in contact with release agents (A1 and A2), similar atomic composition than the prepreg material has been found. However, the XPS analysis of the composite surface cured in contact with release films (F1 and F2) reveals a transfer of fluorine atoms from the release films to the composite surface. Therefore, the composite surface which has been in contact with release films during its curing becomes more electronegative leading to lower the adhesion performance.

Based on these XPS results, G_{IC} and pull-off force results can be explain in more detail. The fluorine transfer, that takes place in F1 y F2 panels, causes the adhesion capacity loss previously measured in G_{IC} tests. Hence, panels cured in contact with release films had lower fracture toughness because the presence of fluorine in the surface, at a difference of the surfaces cured in contact with release agents, which did not have this element and showed better mechanical performance (high G_{IC}).

Table 3. Elemental composition of composites surface measured by XPS.

Ancillary Materials	% O	% F	% Si	% N	% Na	% S	% C
None (prepreg)	22,5	-	2,6	3,7	-	1,5	69,7
Release Agent (A1)	20,2	-	4,4	3,4	-	0,6	71,3
Release Agent (A2)	21,3	-	3,6	4,9	-	1,0	69,2
Release Film (F1)	16,1	20,7	2,6	1,0	0,4	0,5	58,7
Release Film (F2)	20,1	15,8	3,9	3,6	0,2	0,8	55,5

Apart from the mechanical interpretation of the results, during AFM test, the presence of water in the surface of the samples may also play an important role in the adhesion values measured. In the case of hydrophilic surfaces (composite materials in contact with release agents without surface fluorine) the AFM tip interacts with the water layer adsorbed on the composite surface, and the measured adhesion force results from the water layer and Van der Waal forces between the tip and the sample. The total adhesion force is given by the following expression:

$$F_{\text{pull-off}} = F_{\text{cap}} + F_{\text{vdW}}$$

All experiments were done at constant relative humidity of 40 %, which causes the presence of capillary forces in the tip. Many researches have studied the humidity effect on the separation force and they conclude that when humidity is over 20 % the water meniscus is only created in hydrophilic contacts but not in hydrophobic ones [7]. This could explain why pull-off forces in panels cured in contact with release films (F1 y F2) (with hydrophobic zones in their surface owing to fluorine transfer) have smaller values of adhesion forces and why they have greater relative scatter than the pull-off forces of panels cured with release agents (A1 and A2).

CONCLUSIONS

AFM pull-off forces measured in composite panels in contact with release films during curing (7 nN) are smaller than the pull-off forces measured in panels with release agent (12 nN), what correlated well with interlaminar fracture toughness tests as greater adhesion forces indicate better fracture toughness performance.

The lower pull-off forces and poor mechanical behaviour obtained in interlaminar fracture test for the composite in contact with release films during curing, can be attributed to the fluorine transfer from the release films to the composite surface, as it has been determined by XPS tests.

Preliminary AFM results, have shown the potential application of this technique for the understanding of adhesion phenomena, in addition to conventional mechanical testing.

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